

Ant thermal tolerance and behavioural dominance along an altitudinal transect in the Savanna biome: towards a functional classification

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Background

Figure 1 Location of the transect in South Africa and the position of all 44 replicates along the altitudinal transect projected onto a vegetation map (Mucina & Rutherford 2006)

The maintenance of seasonal and daily variation in ant activity patterns allows them to avoid predators and reduce conflict with competitors (Bestelmeyer, 2000). Competition and temperature play a vital role in determining ant assemblage structure. As a result, Andersen (1995) suggested globally generalizable trade-offs between these factors.

Aims

- To characterize dominance hierarchy between ant groups along the transect.
- To quantify the thermal tolerance of the different ant groups.
- Describe the trade-off between dominance and thermal tolerance of the ant groups.
- Test the applicability of Andersen (1995; 1997) ant classification scheme along an elevational transect in a savanna biome.

Table 2 Outcome of aggressive interactions between individuals of ant species groups. Values indicate the percentages of interactions in which an ant was dominant, with the number of interactions between group pair given in parentheses. The dominance indices is the percentage of all interactions in which a group was dominant

Species/groups	PheM	PheG	Tetra	Mono	CreM	CamP	Myrm	SmIM	SmIF	OcyM	LepiS	LargP	TecH	Poly	Dominance Indices
<i>Pheidolemegace</i>		100 (12)	87 (8)	100 (1)							90 (10)			100 (8)	95.5652
<i>Pheidole group</i>		50 (2)	62 (8)	0 (2)	100 (6)		0 (1)	0 (1)			86 (7)	100 (1)		100 (2)	69.9333
<i>Tetramorium</i>				100 (4)	50 (4)		100 (1)								61.5384
<i>Monomorium</i>					0 (1)	50 (2)	33 (3)		86 (7)	100 (1)	80 (5)				37.3255
<i>CreMATogaster</i>					100 (5)	0 (2)							100 (2)		81.8181
<i>Camponotus</i>						0 (2)			0 (1)	33 (3)	50 (2)			0 (3)	17.2285
<i>Myrmicaria</i>															14.2857
<i>Small Myrmicinae</i>											100 (1)	100 (1)			71.5714
<i>Ocymyrmex</i>											33 (3)	100 (4)			44.8235
<i>Lepisiota</i>											50 (2)		40 (5)		29.4
<i>Large Ponerinae</i>												50 (2)			20
<i>Technomyrmex</i>															0
<i>Polyrhachis</i>															25

Methods

Ant activities were observed at baits consisting of cat food in each of the 11 elevational sites (Fig. 1). Baiting was done in November 2011 and April 2012. Ant activity patterns were observed after 15 min, 30 min and 1 hour 3 times during the day and once at night per site. Temperature was recorded using pocket weather tracker, Kestrel 4000 at the start of each baiting session.

Table 1 The taxa and groups examined at baits & the species constituting them organized by Andersen's (1997) functional scheme (with changes that applies to Soutpansberg transect)

Functional Group	Taxon	Species
Dominant Pheidole	<i>Pheidole</i>	<i>Pheidole megacephala</i>
Subordinate Camponotini	<i>Camponotus</i>	<i>C. dofeini</i> , <i>C. fulvipes</i> , <i>C. Niveosetosus</i> & <i>C. mystaceus</i>
Hot climate specialist	<i>Ocymyrmex</i>	<i>Ocymyrmex fortior</i>
Cold climate specialist	<i>Technomyrmex</i>	<i>Technomyrmex sp.01</i>
Generalized Myrmicinae	<i>CreMATogaster</i> , <i>Monomorium</i>	<i>C. sp.01, 02 & 05</i> ; <i>M. damarensis</i> & <i>sp.02</i>
Opportunists	<i>Tetramorium</i> & <i>Myrmicaria</i>	<i>T. sp. 01, 06, 07, & M. natalensis</i>
Cryptic species	<i>Small Myrmicinae</i>	<i>Plagiolipsis sp.01</i> & <i>Oligomyrmex sp.01</i>
Specialist Predators	<i>Large Ponerinae</i>	<i>Odontomachus troglodytes</i> , <i>Pachycondyla sp.03</i> & <i>Platythrea arnoldi</i>

Results

- Overall, 66 species from 22 genera observed at baits. Andersen's (1995; 1997) ant classification scheme does not apply in the Soutpansberg transect (Table 1).
- As expected, the most thermophilic ant was *Ocymyrmex fortior* with its maximum activity at $T_m = 37^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 2)
- The most abundant and aggressive ant (*P. megacephala*) had its maximum activity at $T_m = 10^\circ\text{C}$ together with *Tetramorium* & *Technomyrmex* (Fig. 2; 3 & Table 2)

Figure 2 Proportion of the maximum number of occurrences observed during baiting vs the average temperature recorded at the start of baiting session (T_m , is the average temperature of the cat food bait sessions at which the overall maximum number of occurrences by a group was recorded)

Figure 3 The relationship between the mean temperature of a transect at each group's overall activity maximum and its behavioural dominance indices

Discussion

The existence of trade-offs between dominance and thermal tolerance was not clear as the most dominant ant *P. megacephala* had its maximum activity at lower temperatures. Although this was not the case for the second dominant *CreMATogaster* group. However, the subordinate groups *Ocymyrmex* and *Camponotus* tolerated more extreme temperatures. These trade-offs can be used to define ecological strategies and functional groups along the Soutpansberg Mountains.

References

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